

EDITORIAL

Marginal gains in wound closure: the case for technology-driven bundles and the start of a new Impact Surgery series

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A Surgical site infection: the scale of the problem

Sources: Guest et al. *BMJ Open* 2023; Jenks et al. *J Hosp Infect* 2014; Allegranzi et al. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2016.

Figure 1A. Surgical site infection burden: global incidence and NHS-specific figures. Sources: Guest et al. *BMJ Open* 2023; Jenks et al. *J Hosp Infect* 2014; Allegranzi et al. *Lancet Infect Dis* 2016.

Despite three decades of research, wound complications after gastrointestinal surgery remain an everyday problem in NHS surgical practice. Surgical site infection (SSI) is the most common postoperative complication worldwide, but its burden falls disproportionately on gastrointestinal patients. Colonic surgery alone generates around 39,000 SSIs per year in England, constituting 38% of the national total, at a cost to the NHS of approximately £119 million annually.¹ Inpatient SSI risk following large bowel surgery has ranged as high as 10.5% in UKHSA surveillance data, and although a decade low of 7.9% was recorded in 2021–22, inter-hospital variation remains extreme with 5-year rates across NHS trusts spanning from 0.5% to 23.6% for the same procedure.² However, wound closure encompasses more than just infection, where dehiscence, incisional hernia, time to healing, and patient-reported scar outcomes are all products of closure decisions made in the final minutes of an operation. Looking to the future, technologies that act through mechanical protection, tension

distribution, barrier function and antimicrobial mechanisms require better application to realise a likely benefit.

The inter-hospital variation in SSI rates reflects inconsistency of practice, incomplete bundle adoption, and a surveillance architecture that remains voluntary. Whilst colorectal surgery accounts for 38% of all SSIs nationally, there is no mandatory reporting requirement, whilst in orthopaedic arthroplasty, which together accounts for 5% of SSIs, mandatory surveillance has been present since 2004.¹ Enhanced recovery programmes, WHO SSI prevention guidelines, NICE guidance, and GIRFT review have each contributed to practice at an institutional level, and pockets of genuine excellence exist across the NHS. At a population level, the dial has not moved in proportion to the investment made.

Arthroplasty offers the clearest evidence within surgery that sustained, systematic application of a multi-component approach can drive wound infection rates to levels that gastrointestinal

surgeons would not recognise as achievable. NJR data report SSI rates of 0.34% following primary total knee replacement in the UK,⁵ with Norwegian registry data documenting a statistically significant annual decline in SSI and reoperation for periprosthetic joint infection across 2013–22.⁶ No single intervention produced this outcome; standardised antibiotic prophylaxis, bundled interventions during surgery, meaningful senior leadership, and meticulous attention to documentation of this bundle is more likely to have created the effect. The bundle is therefore the intervention, and even though the cost is higher than doing nothing, it is marginal in terms of total costs and the baseline evidence for bundles is now enough to act.

The global wound closure devices market was valued at approximately \$15 billion in 2024 and is projected to approach \$33 billion by 2035 at a compound annual growth rate of around 7%.⁷ Growth is driven by increasing surgical volume, ageing and more comorbid populations, rising antimicrobial resistance pressure, and expanding adoption of minimally invasive and robotic platforms. For industry and NHS commissioners alike, the opportunity sits at two levels: (1) technologies with sufficient existing evidence where the barrier is implementation and procurement, and (2) technologies where the evidence base requires building, faster and at lower cost than conventional trial methodology has historically allowed.

The marginal gains principle holds that the aggregation of many small improvements, each individually modest and some individually unmeasurable, produces a system-level effect that no single intervention could replicate. Applied to wound closure in gastrointestinal surgery, the relevant question becomes which combination of low-cost, mechanistically rational interventions, applied consistently to a defined high-risk population, will produce a cumulative improvement that no single-component trial is powered or designed to detect. A randomised controlled trial designed to measure the isolated effect of alcohol-chlorhexidine skin preparation,⁸ triclosan-coated sutures,⁹ or a wound edge protector applied in isolation will likely return a neutral result, not because these interventions are without effect, but because their individual effect sizes are small and their value is additive.

Designing trials around isolated bundle components is the wrong unit of analysis and the binary outcome measure of SSI yes/no is crude. The appropriate trial tests the bundle against standard care in a defined high-risk group, with wound complication rate as a composite primary outcome. For low-cost, safe interventions in a marginal gains bundle, formal cost-effectiveness analysis before adoption sets the wrong threshold and is probably withholding patient benefit. When the cost of an intervention is an order of magnitude below the cost of the complication it aims to prevent,

the economic argument for inclusion is structurally sound without a dedicated health economic study. The absence of a published cost-effectiveness analysis is not evidence of cost-ineffectiveness, and treating it as such has been a reason for inaction that this field can no longer afford.

Table 1 maps candidate technologies for a wound closure bundle in high-risk gastrointestinal surgery, graded by the strength of evidence for each component's individual contribution. The principle is that evidence grade reflects confidence in the individual contribution rather than the threshold for bundle inclusion. In a marginal gains framework, all components belong in the bundle; the grade informs the clinician and commissioner how much certainty to place in each when sequencing implementation or making the procurement case. Several components warrant immediate adoption without much further debate. Alcohol-chlorhexidine skin preparation is supported by well-conducted randomised evidence and costs under £2 per patient.⁸ Incisional negative pressure wound therapy carries strong trial evidence in obese and high-risk patients and should be standard in this group, perhaps even for simple surgery (e.g. inguinal hernia repair in the obese). Wound edge protectors have moderate evidence in colorectal and upper gastrointestinal surgery. Triclosan-coated sutures appear in WHO 2018 SSI prevention guidelines on the basis of meta-analytic data.^{9,10} The aggregate cost of these four components is modest against the £3,500–£5,200 NHS cost per SSI episode they aim to prevent.³ Where an intervention is safe and inexpensive, the burden of proof for exclusion from a marginal gains bundle exceeds the burden of proof for inclusion.

The conventional single-component randomised trial will not resolve the evidence gaps in Table 1 within a useful timeframe, and it is in any case the wrong design for evaluating a bundle strategy. Digital surgical twin RCTs, local evaluations, faster regional bundle trials with more sophisticated outcome measures are the next steps in producing patient benefit. This does not lower evidentiary standards but generates adequate evidence more efficiently, closing the gap between mechanistic rationale and clinical adoption.

Enough is known to act and the marginal gains approach to wound closure in high-risk gastrointestinal surgery does not require new evidence for its foundation components. This new Impact Surgery series will unpick and develop the rationale and evidence for faster inclusion of technologies into wound closure portfolios around the world; register for free and keep reading. We hope to bridge the gap between emerging technologies on the market, what surgeons know, and how procurement gaps can be closed.

B The commercial opportunity: global wound closure devices market

USD billion — analyst estimates (Grand View Research; Spherical Insights, 2024–35)

Growth driven by: surgical volume growth, ageing populations, antimicrobial resistance pressure, shift from open to minimally invasive and robotic surgery
 CAGR = compound annual growth rate. MIS = minimally invasive surgery. Figures are indicative across analyst estimates.

Figure 1B. The commercial opportunity: global wound closure devices market, 2024–35. Sources: Grand View Research; Spherical Insights.⁷

Technology	Mechanism	Cost indicator	Grade
Alcohol-chlorhexidine skin preparation	Reduces skin flora at incision site; superior to povidone-iodine	< £2	Strong
Triclosan-coated sutures fascial and subcutaneous closure	Antimicrobial coating reduces biofilm formation at suture line	£5–15	Moderate
Wound edge protector plastic ring retractor, open surgery	Shields wound margin from luminal contamination	£10–25	Moderate
Incisional NPWT closed incision negative pressure	Reduces haematoma, oedema, and dead space at incision	£50–150	Strong
Wound irrigation aqueous iodine or saline	Mechanical and antiseptic reduction of wound bioburden	< £5	Emerging
Antimicrobial dressings silver, iodine, or DACC-coated	Sustained antimicrobial activity at the wound surface post-closure	£10–40	Emerging
Tissue adhesives cyanoacrylate, skin layer only	Rapid skin seal; barrier to exogenous bacterial ingress	£5–20	Limited
Intelligent closure devices sensor-enabled, adaptive tension	Real-time tension monitoring; adaptive fascial approximation	TBC	Limited

Strong | Moderate | Emerging | Limited

Table 1. Candidate technologies for a marginal gains wound closure bundle in high-risk gastrointestinal surgery. Evidence grading is provisional; formal grading with systematic review will appear in dedicated series issues.

All components included on marginal gains principles; grade reflects confidence in individual contribution, not inclusion threshold. DACC = dialkylcarbomoyl chloride. NPWT = negative pressure wound therapy. TBC = to be confirmed as devices reach market.

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